

Gradient and Energy Flow in Quantum Mechanics

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In previous notes, we have argued that the classical statement $P(x)dx = dx/L$, where L is length, is associated with the uniform distribution of stationary objects in L . Given that $d/dx P(x) = 0$, one could have nonzero $Pd(px)$ and $Pd(-px)$ which would satisfy this equation if: $P(x) = Pd(px)Pd(-px)$ and $d/dx Pd(px) = \text{constant } p P(d(px))$. In other words, the gradient is associated with energy flow, p (momentum), in the case of constant p .

What happens if one has a bound object? In such a case, one does not have $P(x) = 1/L$. One would, however, have an object localized in a certain spatial region and this center may be placed at any x with the same probability, so there is again a translational invariance, but this time of the center of mass. Thus, one expects $\exp(-iEt + i P_{cm} x)$ where $P_{cm} = 0$. The question is what does one do for the non-center of mass portion? If one has a probability $Pd(px)$ for a constant p , one might assume a probability $W(x)$ for a bound state such that $W^*(x)W(x)$ represents a kind of classical probability. Without using $W(x) = \sum \text{over } p a(p)\exp(ipx)$, we try to determine the conditions which $W(x)$ should satisfy. In such a case, one might expect average energy conservation to hold, but it is not clear how to write the kinetic energy. For example, for the $p = \text{constant}$ case, one might use: $d/dx d/dx \exp(ipx) / \exp(ipx)$ or $d/dx \exp(ipx) d/dx \exp(ipx) / \{ \exp(ipx)\exp(ipx) \}$. One may also note that $\exp(ipx)$ s are orthogonal in x for different p 's and that one might expect $W_n(x)$ s to also be orthogonal in x . We try to give arguments for choosing $-\text{grad} \cdot \text{grad } W / W$ ($\hbar^2/2m$) as the kinetic energy which then leads to an equation which automatically leads to orthogonality. We argue that if a probability $W(x)$ exists, then $\text{grad } W$ should be proportional to energy flow (momentum) like $d/dx \exp(ipx)$. We suggest that this is the basic assumption for solving a bound problem, i.e. one with a potential $V(x)$.

Free Particle

The classical probability of a free particle is: $P(x)dx = dx/L$ ((1)) where L is length. This represents a classical uniform distribution for a stationary object. We argued in previous notes that a $p, -p$ (constant momenta) pair is like a stationary object, so $Pd(px) Pd(-px) = P(x)$ which leads to $\exp(ipx)$ as a possible solution which neither grows or shrinks indefinitely.

One may observe immediately that $d/dx \exp(ipx) = ip \exp(ipx)$, i.e. the translational operator d/dx acting on the dynamic probability. Thus, the dynamics of the problem are linked with the gradient and a square root kind of dynamic probability.

We use this basic assumption and try to apply it to a bound state instead of using $W(x) = \sum \text{over } p a(p)\exp(ipx)$.

Bound State

We assume that there exists a dynamic type of probability $W(x)$ such that $W^*(x)W(x)$ represents a classical type of probability. We note that $W(x)$ must tend to 0 at $\pm \infty$ in order that a particle be localized in some x region. We also note that the center-of-mass of the bound

system may occur at any x with the same probability so there is translational invariance of the center-of-mass. This implies that:

$$\exp(-iE_{cm} t + i p_{cm} x) \text{ with } p_{cm}=0 \text{ holds } ((1))$$

We suggest that within the bound region: $dW/dx / W =$ a kind of average momentum $((2))$

The question becomes: How does compute W ? Before considering this, we note that $\exp(ipx)$ s are orthogonal in x for different p values and so it might be good if $W_n(x)$'s were also orthogonal in x for different n (energy values). This is a consideration together with the classical idea that average energy is constant at each x .

If $((2))$ holds, then it seems one would write:

$$-1/2 m \hbar \text{grad } W \cdot \text{grad } W / (WW) = (E-V(x)) \quad ((3))$$

A possible objection is that dynamics should be associated with W , but WW in the denominator is the classical type density. For a free particle, $P(x) = 1/L$ does not demonstrate any dynamics and so it is not clear why WW should appear in $((3))$. This argument, however, is not strong enough perhaps to dismiss $((3))$. Furthermore, $((2))$ must be respected.

We first note that $((3))$ cannot be correct. For the case of an oscillator, $V(x)=.5kx^2$ which is 0 at $x=0$. If one has a ground state, then one might expect a symmetric crest about $x=0$ which has 0 d/dx slope. Thus, $((3))$ yields: $0 = E$ which cannot be. Thus, one cannot use $((3))$, but one cannot dismiss $((2))$ either.

A resolution is to note that one may integrate $((3))$ multiplies by WW . This yields the same result as integrating (using integration of parts and $W(x)=0$ at $x=\pm$ infinite).

$$-1/2m \hbar \text{grad } \dot{\text{grad}} W / W = (E-V(x)) \quad ((4))$$

$((4))$ now only uses $W(x)$, the dynamic probability, not WW . Multiplying by W^*W and integrating yields the dx integral of $((3))$. Thus, $((2))$ is respected, but $((4))$ does not have the $x=0$, $dW/dx =0$ contradiction of $((3))$.

Finally, one may ask whether different W_n 's corresponding to different E_n 's are orthogonal in x . Again, the idea of integration by parts used directly above is useful.

$$\text{As shown in many textbooks: } W_2^* (-1/2m \hbar \text{grad } \dot{\text{grad}} W_1) = W_2(E_1-V) W_1 \quad ((5))$$

minus $((5))$ with 1 and 2 interchanged yields: $0 = (E_1-E_2) \int W_2^* W_1 dx$ so W_1 and W_2 are orthogonal in x space.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that for the classical $P(x)=1/L$, i.e. the uniform distribution of stationary objects, one has the relation: $dP/dx=0$, where d/dx is the translational generator. If one wishes to introduce dynamics, one may do so using constant p , $-p$ at each x through $P=Pd(px)Pd(-px)$ if $d/dx Pd(px) = \text{constant } p Pd(px)$. This leads to a dynamic square root type probability $\exp(ipx)$. The key idea is that $d/dx Pd(px) = p Pd(px)$. Given this result, however, it is not clear how to calculate kinetic energy. One may write: $\{ d/dx \exp(ipx) d/dx \exp(ipx) \} / (\exp(ipx) \exp(ipx))$ or $\{d/dx d/dx \exp(ipx) \} / \exp(ipx)$. Given that the latter only uses the dynamic probability $\exp(ipx)$, it seems that this should be chosen, but this may not be a strong enough argument.

We next consider a bound state and do not use $W(x)=\text{Sum over } p a(p)\exp(ipx)$. We postulate a $W(x)$ such that $d/dx W(x) / W(x) = \text{constant} * \text{a kind of momentum}$. $W(x)$ must tend to 0 at \pm infinite for the object to be localized. We next suggest that average kinetic energy $+ V(x)=E$ at each x , but what should be used for kinetic energy? One may try $-1/2m \hbar \hbar \text{grad} W \text{ dot grad} W / WW$ or $-1/2m \hbar \hbar \text{grad grad } W / W$. We prefer the latter because it only uses the dynamic probability W , but if one uses the former, then $dW/dx=0$ means that $E-V(x) = 0$, but this cannot be the case for the ground state of an oscillator, if the oscillator ground state is a symmetric crest about $x=0$. A symmetric crest about $x=0$ cannot have 0 energy. Thus, one might try using $KE \text{ ave} = -1/2m \hbar \hbar \text{grad dot grad } W / W$, but $dW/dx / W = \text{constant} * \text{momentum}$ must be respected. If one multiplies: $KE \text{ ave} + V(x) = E$ by WW using $\text{grad dot grad } W$, then it yields the same result as using $\text{grad } W \text{ dot grad } W / WW$ and multiplying the equation by $W*W$. Thus, the basic assumption $dW/dx / W = \text{constant } W$ is still present.

One may also show that using $\text{grad dot grad } W$ to calculate $KE \text{ ave}$ leads to orthogonal $W_n(x)$'s in x as is shown in many textbooks.